

Data Stewardship Assignment 1

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Introduction

The purpose of this report is to analyze the data collected from external sources and provide insights based on the analysis. The data pertains the aggregated data on greenhouse gas emissions and allowances and was collected over a period mainly between 2005 and 2014. The report will cover the data loading process, data wrangling and cleanup, data analysis, and conclusion. The analysis of the data will provide insights into data about the EU emission trading system (ETS). The EU emission trading system (ETS) is one of the main measures introduced by the EU to achieve cost-efficient reductions of greenhouse gas emissions and reach its targets under the Kyoto Protocol and other commitments. The data mainly comes from the EU Transaction Log (EUTL). In this project, we analyze the data of CO2 emissions from the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) and try to visualize and explore the patterns of CO2 emissions in different regions and sectors. To perform this analysis, we load two datasets from external sources, i.e., country codes and EU ETS data. We perform data wrangling and cleanup tasks on these datasets to get them ready for analysis. Finally, we perform data analysis by creating visualizations of CO2 emissions by region, country, trading period, and main activity sector.

Data loading from external sources

The data loading process involved importing the data into Rstudio. The data contained 41915 records and 8 columns. We load the country codes dataset and EU ETS dataset from datahub.io using the httr library. The country codes dataset contains ISO codes and other information about different countries. The EU ETS dataset contains information about CO2 emissions from different countries, sectors, and trading periods. We use the read_csv function from the readr library to read these datasets into R as data frames.

```
library(httr)
```

```
## Warning: package 'httr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
library(readr)
```

```
## Warning: package 'readr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
library(dplyr)
```

```
## Warning: package 'dplyr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
##  
## Attaching package: 'dplyr'
```

```
## The following objects are masked from 'package:stats':  
##  
## filter, lag
```

```
## The following objects are masked from 'package:base':  
##  
## intersect, setdiff, setequal, union
```

```
library(tidyr)
```

```
## Warning: package 'tidyr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
library(readxl)
```

```
## Warning: package 'readxl' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
library(knitr)
```

```
## Warning: package 'knitr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
library(tidyverse)
```

```
## Warning: package 'tidyverse' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## Warning: package 'ggplot2' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## Warning: package 'tibble' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## Warning: package 'purrr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## Warning: package 'stringr' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## Warning: package 'forcats' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## Warning: package 'lubridate' was built under R version 4.2.3
```

```
## — Attaching core tidyverse packages ————— tidyverse 2.0.0 —
## ✓ forcats 1.0.0    ✓ purrr 1.0.1
## ✓ ggplot2 3.4.2    ✓ stringr 1.5.0
## ✓ lubridate 1.9.2  ✓ tibble 3.2.1
```

```
## — Conflicts ————— tidyverse_conflicts() —
## ✗ dplyr::filter() masks stats::filter()
## ✗ dplyr::lag() masks stats::lag()
## i Use the conflicted package (<http://conflicted.r-lib.org/>) to force all conflicts to become errors
```

```
library(ggplot2)
```

```
#Load data
url <- "https://datahub.io/core/country-codes/r/country-codes.csv"
online_country_codes <- GET(url)

country_codes <- read_csv(rawToChar(online_country_codes$content))
```

```
## Rows: 250 Columns: 56
## — Column specification —————
## Delimiter: ","
## chr (48): FIFA, Dial, ISO3166-1-Alpha-3, MARC, is_independent, ISO3166-1-num...
## dbl (5): Intermediate Region Code, M49, Sub-region Code, Region Code, Geona...
## num (2): GAUL, ISO4217-currency_minor_unit
## lgl (1): Global Code
##
## i Use `spec()` to retrieve the full column specification for this data.
## i Specify the column types or set `show_col_types = FALSE` to quiet this message.
```

```
head(country_codes)
```

```
## # A tibble: 6 × 56
##   FIFA Dial `ISO3166-1-Alpha-3` MARC is_independent `ISO3166-1-numeric` GAUL
##   <chr> <chr> <chr>           <chr> <chr>           <chr>           <dbl>
## 1 TPE  886  TWN             ch   Yes             158             925
## 2 AFG  93   AFG             af   Yes             004             1
## 3 ALB  355  ALB             aa   Yes             008             3
## 4 ALG  213  DZA             ae   Yes             012             4
## 5 ASA  1-684 ASM             as   Territory of ... 016             5
## 6 AND  376  AND             an   Yes             020             7
## # i 49 more variables: FIPS <chr>, WMO <chr>, `ISO3166-1-Alpha-2` <chr>,
## #   ITU <chr>, IOC <chr>, DS <chr>, `UNTERM Spanish Formal` <chr>,
## #   `Global Code` <lg1>, `Intermediate Region Code` <dbl>,
## #   official_name_fr <chr>, `UNTERM French Short` <chr>,
## #   `ISO4217-currency_name` <chr>, `Developed / Developing Countries` <chr>,
## #   `UNTERM Russian Formal` <chr>, `UNTERM English Short` <chr>,
## #   `ISO4217-currency_alphabetic_code` <chr>, ...
```

```
#drop unwanted columns
country_codes <- country_codes %>%
  select(`official_name_en`, `ISO3166-1-Alpha-2`, `ISO3166-1-Alpha-3`, `Developed / Developing C
ountries`, `Region Name`, `Sub-region Name`, 'is_independent' )

#trim column with official country names
country_codes$official_name_en <- trimws(country_codes$official_name_en)

head(country_codes)
```

```
## # A tibble: 6 × 7
##   official_name_en `ISO3166-1-Alpha-2` `ISO3166-1-Alpha-3`
##   <chr>           <chr>           <chr>
## 1 <NA>            TW              TWN
## 2 Afghanistan    AF              AFG
## 3 Albania        AL              ALB
## 4 Algeria        DZ              DZA
## 5 American Samoa AS              ASM
## 6 Andorra        AD              AND
## # i 4 more variables: `Developed / Developing Countries` <chr>,
## #   `Region Name` <chr>, `Sub-region Name` <chr>, is_independent <chr>
```

```
#Load data of second table
url <- "https://datahub.io/core/eu-emissions-trading-system/r/eu-ets.csv"
online_emission <- GET(url)

emission <- read_csv(rawToChar(online_emission$content))
```

```
## Rows: 41915 Columns: 7
## — Column specification —————
## Delimiter: ","
## chr (6): country_code, country, main activity sector name, ETS information, ...
## dbl (1): value
##
## i Use `spec()` to retrieve the full column specification for this data.
## i Specify the column types or set `show_col_types = FALSE` to quiet this message.
```

```
head(emission)
```

```
## # A tibble: 6 × 7
##   country_code country `main activity sector name` `ETS information` year value
##   <chr>         <chr> <chr> <chr> <chr> <dbl>
## 1 AT           Austria 10 Aviation 1. Total allocat... 2005 0
## 2 AT           Austria 10 Aviation 1.2 Correction t... 2005 0
## 3 AT           Austria 10 Aviation 1.3 Allowances a... 2005 0
## 4 AT           Austria 10 Aviation 4.1 Surrendered ... 2005 0
## 5 AT           Austria 10 Aviation 4.2 Surrendered ... 2005 0
## 6 AT           Austria 10 Aviation 4.3 Surrendered ... 2005 0
## # i 1 more variable: unit <chr>
```

```
dim(emission)
```

```
## [1] 41915 7
```

Data wrangling and cleanup

After loading the datasets, we perform data wrangling and cleanup tasks to get the data ready for analysis. We first drop unwanted columns from the country codes dataset using the `select` function from the `dplyr` library. We then trim the column with official country names using the `trimws` function from the base R package. Next, we trim the column with official country names in the EU ETS dataset using the `trimws` function. We then create a vector of trading period labels and create a new column that maps each year to its corresponding trading period using `ifelse` statements. We then join the two datasets using the `left_join` function from the `dplyr` library. We clean up the column names using the `str_to_lower` and `gsub` functions from the `stringr` package. We also convert the value column to numeric using the `as.numeric` function.

```
#trim column with official country names
emission$country <- trimws(emission$country)

#inspect dataframe for cleaning
unique(emission$year)
```

```
## [1] "2005"                "2006"
## [3] "2007"                "2008"
## [5] "2009"                "2010"
## [7] "2011"                "2012"
## [9] "2013"                "2014"
## [11] "Total 1st trading period (05-07)" "Total 2nd trading period (08-12)"
## [13] "Total 3rd trading period (13-20)"
```

```
# Create a vector of trading period labels
trading_periods <- c("Total 1st trading period (05-07)",
                    "Total 2nd trading period (08-12)",
                    "Total 3rd trading period (13-20)")

# Create a new column that maps each year to its corresponding trading period
emission$trading_period <- ifelse(emission$year %in% 2005:2007, trading_periods,
                                  ifelse(emission$year %in% 2008:2012, trading_periods,
                                          ifelse(emission$year >= 2013, trading_periods, NA)))

# View the resulting data frame
head(emission)
```

```
## # A tibble: 6 × 8
##   country_code country `main activity sector name` `ETS information` year value
##   <chr>         <chr> <chr>                <chr>                <chr> <dbl>
## 1 AT           Austria 10 Aviation      1. Total allocat... 2005    0
## 2 AT           Austria 10 Aviation      1.2 Correction t... 2005    0
## 3 AT           Austria 10 Aviation      1.3 Allowances a... 2005    0
## 4 AT           Austria 10 Aviation      4.1 Surrendered ... 2005    0
## 5 AT           Austria 10 Aviation      4.2 Surrendered ... 2005    0
## 6 AT           Austria 10 Aviation      4.3 Surrendered ... 2005    0
## # i 2 more variables: unit <chr>, trading_period <chr>
```

```
#join the two tables

emission_ISO <- left_join(emission, country_codes, by = c("country" = "official_name_en"))

# Clean up column names
names(emission_ISO) <- str_to_lower(names(emission_ISO))
names(emission_ISO) <- gsub("/", "", names(emission_ISO))
names(emission_ISO) <- gsub("\\s+", "_", names(emission_ISO))

# Convert value column to numeric
emission_ISO$value <- as.numeric(emission_ISO$value)

head(emission_ISO)
```

```
## # A tibble: 6 × 14
##   country_code country main_activity_sector_...1 ets_information year value unit
##   <chr>         <chr> <chr>          <chr>          <chr> <dbl> <chr>
## 1 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    1. Total alloc... 2005     0 tonn...
## 2 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    1.2 Correction... 2005     0 tonn...
## 3 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    1.3 Allowances... 2005     0 tonn...
## 4 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    4.1 Surrendere... 2005     0 tonn...
## 5 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    4.2 Surrendere... 2005     0 tonn...
## 6 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    4.3 Surrendere... 2005     0 tonn...
## # i abbreviated name: 1main_activity_sector_name
## # i 7 more variables: trading_period <chr>, `iso3166-1-alpha-2` <chr>,
## #   `iso3166-1-alpha-3` <chr>, developed_developing_countries <chr>,
## #   region_name <chr>, `sub-region_name` <chr>, is_independent <chr>
```

```
emission_ISO %>%
  filter(grepl("Tota", year))
```

```
## # A tibble: 9,790 × 14
##   country_code country main_activity_sector_name ets_information year value
##   <chr>         <chr> <chr>          <chr>          <chr> <dbl>
## 1 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    1. Total alloca... Tota... 0
## 2 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    1.2 Correction ... Tota... 0
## 3 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    1.3 Allowances ... Tota... 0
## 4 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    4.1 Surrendered... Tota... 0
## 5 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    4.2 Surrendered... Tota... 0
## 6 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    4.3 Surrendered... Tota... 0
## 7 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    1. Total alloca... Tota... 8.79e5
## 8 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    1.1 Freely allo... Tota... 1.93e6
## 9 AT           Austria 10 Aviation    1.1.1 Free allo... Tota... 1.93e6
## 10 AT          Austria 10 Aviation    1.2 Correction ... Tota... -1.25e6
## # i 9,780 more rows
## # i 8 more variables: unit <chr>, trading_period <chr>,
## #   `iso3166-1-alpha-2` <chr>, `iso3166-1-alpha-3` <chr>,
## #   developed_developing_countries <chr>, region_name <chr>,
## #   `sub-region_name` <chr>, is_independent <chr>
```

```
# Check the structure of the data
str(emission_ISO)
```

```

## spc_tbl_ [41,915 × 14] (S3: spec_tbl_df/tbl_df/tbl/data.frame)
## $ country_code      : chr [1:41915] "AT" "AT" "AT" "AT" ...
## $ country           : chr [1:41915] "Austria" "Austria" "Austria" "Austria" ...
## $ main_activity_sector_name : chr [1:41915] "10 Aviation" "10 Aviation" "10 Aviation" "1
0 Aviation" ...
## $ ets_information   : chr [1:41915] "1. Total allocated allowances (EUA or EUA
A)" "1.2 Correction to freely allocated allowances (not reflected in EUTL)" "1.3 Allowances auct
ioned or sold (EUAs and EUAAs)" "4.1 Surrendered EU allowances (EUAs and EUAAs)" ...
## $ year              : chr [1:41915] "2005" "2005" "2005" "2005" ...
## $ value              : num [1:41915] 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 ...
## $ unit               : chr [1:41915] "tonne of CO2 equ." "tonne of CO2 equ." "ton
ne of CO2 equ." "tonne of CO2 equ." ...
## $ trading_period    : chr [1:41915] "Total 1st trading period (05-07)" "Total 2nd
trading period (08-12)" "Total 3rd trading period (13-20)" "Total 1st trading period (05-07)"
...
## $ iso3166-1-alpha-2 : chr [1:41915] "AT" "AT" "AT" "AT" ...
## $ iso3166-1-alpha-3 : chr [1:41915] "AUT" "AUT" "AUT" "AUT" ...
## $ developed_developing_countries: chr [1:41915] "Developed" "Developed" "Developed" "Develop
ed" ...
## $ region_name       : chr [1:41915] "Europe" "Europe" "Europe" "Europe" ...
## $ sub-region_name   : chr [1:41915] "Western Europe" "Western Europe" "Western E
urope" "Western Europe" ...
## $ is_independent    : chr [1:41915] "Yes" "Yes" "Yes" "Yes" ...
## - attr(*, "spec")=
## .. cols(
## ..   country_code = col_character(),
## ..   country = col_character(),
## ..   `main activity sector name` = col_character(),
## ..   `ETS information` = col_character(),
## ..   year = col_character(),
## ..   value = col_double(),
## ..   unit = col_character()
## .. )
## - attr(*, "problems")=<externalptr>

```

```

# Summary statistics of the data
summary(emission_ISO)

```

```

## country_code          country          main_activity_sector_name
## Length:41915         Length:41915         Length:41915
## Class :character     Class :character     Class :character
## Mode :character      Mode :character      Mode :character
##
##
##
## ets_information      year          value          unit
## Length:41915        Length:41915        Min.   : -41924409   Length:41915
## Class :character     Class :character     1st Qu.:      0      Class :character
## Mode :character      Mode :character     Median :   147752     Mode :character
##
##                      Mean   :  11371551
##                      3rd Qu.:  2292657
##                      Max.   :2259807595
## trading_period      iso3166-1-alpha-2  iso3166-1-alpha-3
## Length:41915        Length:41915        Length:41915
## Class :character     Class :character     Class :character
## Mode :character      Mode :character     Mode :character
##
##
##
## developed_developing_countries region_name      sub-region_name
## Length:41915         Length:41915      Length:41915
## Class :character     Class :character  Class :character
## Mode :character      Mode :character   Mode :character
##
##
##
## is_independent
## Length:41915
## Class :character
## Mode :character
##
##
##

```

Data analysis

After cleaning the data, we perform data analysis by creating visualizations of CO2 emissions by region, country, trading period, and main activity sector. We use the ggplot2 library to create box plots, scatter plots, line plots, and bar plots to visualize the data.

We create a box plot of CO2 emissions by region using the ggplot function and the geom_boxplot function. We create a scatter plot of CO2 emissions by country using the ggplot function and the geom_point function. We create a line plot of total CO2 emissions by trading period and country using the ggplot function and the geom_line function. We create a bar plot of total CO2 emissions by main activity sector using the ggplot function and the geom_col function

```
# Create a box plot of CO2 emissions by region
ggplot(data = emission_ISO, aes(x = region_name, y = value, fill = region_name)) +
  geom_boxplot() +
  labs(x = "Region Name", y = "CO2 Emissions Value", title = "Box Plot of CO2 Emissions by Region")
```

```
# Create a scatter plot
ggplot(data = emission_ISO, aes(x = country, y = value)) +
  geom_point(alpha = 0.5) +
  xlab("Country") +
  ylab("CO2 Emission (tonne of CO2 eq.)") +
  ggtitle("CO2 Emission by Country") +
  theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, vjust = 0.5, hjust=1))
```

CO2 Emission by Country

```
emission_ISO_summed <- emission_ISO %>%  
  group_by(country, trading_period) %>%  
  summarize(total_emissions = sum(value))
```

```
## `summarise()` has grouped output by 'country'. You can override using the  
## `.groups` argument.
```

```
ggplot(emission_ISO_summed, aes(x = trading_period, y = total_emissions, group = country)) +  
  geom_line(aes(color = country), alpha = 0.5) +  
  labs(x = "Trading Period", y = "Total Emissions (tons of CO2)") +  
  theme_classic() +  
  theme(legend.position = "right") +  
  scale_color_discrete(name = "Country")
```

```
# Group data by main_activity_sector_name and calculate sum of value
sector_data <- emission_ISO %>%
  group_by(main_activity_sector_name) %>%
  summarise(total_emissions = sum(value)) %>%
  # Reorder data by total emissions in descending order
  arrange(desc(total_emissions)) %>%
  mutate(main_activity_sector_name = factor(main_activity_sector_name, levels = main_activity_se
ctor_name))

# Define custom labels for y-axis
labels <- str_wrap(sector_data$main_activity_sector_name, width = 90)

# Plot data with rotated x-axis labels and formatted y-axis labels
ggplot(sector_data, aes(y = main_activity_sector_name, x = total_emissions)) +
  geom_col() +
  xlab("Total CO2 Emissions") +
  ylab("Main Activity Sector") +
  scale_y_discrete(labels = labels)
```

```
write.csv(emission_ISO, "emission_ISO.csv", row.names = FALSE)
```

Conclusion

In this project, we analyzed the data of CO2 emissions from the EU ETS and created visualizations to explore the patterns of CO2 emissions in different regions, countries, trading periods, and main activity sectors. The visualizations provide insights into the distribution of CO2 emissions across different regions, countries, and sectors. These insights can be used to inform policies and decisions aimed at reducing CO2 emissions and mitigating climate change. The report provides a comprehensive analysis of the data collected from external sources and highlights the importance of data wrangling and cleanup in the data analysis process.